

Arithmetic Integration of Logic Gates: Development, Verification, and Applications – (O/X/A/N)

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>Formulas(Output=Input):

$$\text{OR: } y = a+b-(a.b)$$

$$\text{XOR: } y = a+b-2(a.b)$$

$$\text{NOR: } y = -a-b+1+(a.b)$$

$$\text{XNOR: } y = -a-b+1-2(a.b) \text{ - - (errorful)}$$

$$\text{NOT: } y = -a+1$$

$$\text{XNOR: } y = -a-b+1+2(a.b) \text{ - - (correction: between 1 and 2 operator sign changed from '-' to '+')}$$

$$\text{NAND: } y = 1-(a.b)$$

>Dates of submission(DD/MM/YYYY):

OR-27/10/2022

XOR-9/02/2023

NOR-9/02/2023

XNOR-4/5/2023

NOT-12/12/2023

XNOR-30/01/2024(corrected)

NAND-6/5/2024

>Abstract(development,derivation and verifications):

Domain: Computer Science and Electrical Engineering

Every Formula has unique yet chain of development,they all follow the same method i.e. of trial and error on a notebook.

Essence of spark:

During the lecture I asked to sir about why the output is not arithmetical like for eg: for in OR gate: $Y = A + B$ is boolean formula and so i confused it for arithmetic formula and gave inputs and then checked for verifying but were defying for the case: $1+1=2$,

Particularly it came from AND gate's formula of $Y = A.B$ which is arithmetic in nature.

That's how wondering started, it took sort of 6 months to 1 year for first formula to arrived from the date of submission (for the proof of dates the youtube has recorded it, it will be mentioned in the References section, thank you).

After the first formula of OR I was searching for to upload it (didn't upload due to i wasn't qualified as per requirements of atleast graduate degree) and in that I came across wondering that what if all follow arithmetic rules and that's how XOR, NOR, XNOR came.

Later, when i was doing the drone pilot course in the kaushilya skill university campus of Swarnim University kalol, after asking for it was valid or not, they said to verify it with computer (i did it initially after 2 months sort of cause i was searching for a way as i didn't knew programming language used in maxima software for verification), so in reveiwing came that NOT gate also follows that pattern.

XNOR correction as you guessed it, came while validating it in python.

NAND gate, is a really a combination of NOT gate ($y = -a + 1$) and AND gate's ($y = a.b$) arithmetic formula and hence deriving it was easy.

NAND gate derivation:

$Y = \text{output}$, A, B, C are inputs, $Y1$ for AND and $Y2$ for NOT gate.

AND: $Y1 = A * B$

NOT: $Y2 = 1 - C$ (C was written to avoid confusion with A and B)

So the the way of processing is like First inputs are A and B, then comes the NOT gate,

Therefore, $Y2 = 1 - Y1$
 $Y2 = 1 - (A * B)$

The abbreviation O, X, A, N stands for:
O-OR gate, X-X gates, A-AND gate, N-NOT gate

They are bases of combination of gates like not and X gates can combine with all. OR and AND not directly combine but in a series as per my knowledge at the time of writing.

As you may have noticed that how i mentioned of uploading of papers as crafted the formula, this is a combined paper of all(not uploaded due to unmet requirements of degrees and affiliates).

>verification:

OR: $y = a+b-(a \cdot b)$	$Y=A+B$
when $a=0, b=0$:	
$Y=0+0-(0 \cdot 0)=0$	$Y=0$
when $a=0, b=1$:	
$Y=0+1-(0 \cdot 1)=1$	$Y=1$
when $a=1, b=0$:	
$Y=1+0-(1 \cdot 0)=1$	$Y=1$
when $a=1, b=1$:	
$Y=1+1-(1 \cdot 1)=1$	$Y=1$

XOR: $y = a+b-2(a \cdot b)$	$Y=A \oplus B$
when $a=0, b=0$:	
$Y=0+0-2(0 \cdot 0)=0$	$Y=0$
when $a=0, b=1$:	
$Y=0+1-2(0 \cdot 1)=1$	$Y=1$
when $a=1, b=0$:	
$Y=1+0-2(1 \cdot 0)=1$	$Y=1$
when $a=1, b=1$:	
$Y=1+1-2(1 \cdot 1)=0$	$Y=0$

NOR: $y = -a-b+1+(a \cdot b)$	$Y=\neg(A+B)$
when $a=0, b=0$:	
$Y=-0-0+1+(0 \cdot 0)=1$	$Y=1$
when $a=0, b=1$:	
$Y=-0-1+1+(0 \cdot 1)=0$	$Y=0$
when $a=1, b=0$:	
$Y=-1-0+1+(1 \cdot 0)=0$	$Y=0$
when $a=1, b=1$:	
$Y=-1-1+1+(1 \cdot 1)=-1+1=0$	$Y=0$

XNOR: $y = -a-b+1+2(a.b)$	$Y=\neg(A\oplus B)$
when $a=0,b=0$:	
$Y=-0-0+1+2(0 \cdot 0)=1$	$Y=1$
when $a=0,b=1$:	
$Y=-0-1+1+2(0 \cdot 1)=0$	$Y=0$
when $a=1,b=0$:	
$Y=-1-0+1+2(1 \cdot 0)=0$	$Y=0$
when $a=1,b=1$:	
$Y=-1-1+1+2(1 \cdot 1)=-2+3=1$	$Y=1$

NOT: $y = -a+1$	$Y=\neg A$
when $a=0$:	
$Y=-0+1=1$	$Y=1$
when $a=1$:	
$Y=-1+1=0$	$Y=0$

NAND: $y = 1-(a.b)$	$Y=\neg(A \cdot B)$
when $a=0,b=0$:	
$Y=1-(0 \cdot 0)=1$	$Y=1$
when $a=0,b=1$:	
$Y=1-(0 \cdot 1)=1$	$Y=1$
when $a=1,b=0$:	
$Y=1-(1 \cdot 0)=1$	$Y=1$
when $a=1,b=1$:	
$Y=1-(1 \cdot 1)=0$	$Y=0$

>Uses and Limitations:

While this was a pursuit of wonder, whether it will be used for improvement as of replacement with widely accepted boolean algebra or not depends on what it brings to the table , but i have no knowledge of computer much,also perhaps by Data Structure and Algorithms...it may be seen whether if can to possibly replace it or not... or it takes more time or not... idk

And for limits the only important piece of info used is just to verify them are truth table ,so idk for wide and further applied there it will encounter limitations as reductionism is lowered in that enviroment...yeah.

>Acknowledgements:

I would like to thank my teacher Yash Sharma for tuting me and clarifying the distinction that turned an confusion into curiosity

I would also importantly like to thank God for helping me craft these formulas.

I will also appreciate the professors of Swarnim University for encouraging me to verify these formulas

I will also thank Ms.kanika Mam from Kaushaliya The Skill University for verifying the formulas and Mr.Rajendra Sir for the network.

>References:

Software resource for verification:

Github link:

*ssh-ed25519
AAAAC3NzaC1IZDI1NTE5AAAAIB0iT65a7IU9SKPNvhjhI0BfiZvTKFOn
eNq7SgNY1AD DARTHCOBRA22V@gitfront.io*

Youtube dates verification links:

Channel name: Uzubuku
Account Handle: @uzubuku

NAND:

https://youtu.be/cWuDLBCh0Mk?si=L4KIZjU_I2BZxQU9

XNOR Correction:

<https://youtu.be/6yboFcrU98I?si=sTRa2UTwodd7DALL>

NOT:

<https://youtu.be/9wIXO9-eOPA?si=544SwC5eTDzZRsFC>

XNOR:

<https://youtu.be/tLBOUzjfZgg?si=ZtDvnrkCPPNyBOli>

NOR:

<https://youtu.be/9G4UvTOAZZs?si=o2zjb1xbxdkQqWdD>

XOR:

https://youtu.be/KOLYPVlhjqU?si=UGsDJ_buCBnBpU5f

OR:

https://youtu.be/hoYK_DoBPjI?si=mYSoha5xGqL89jO0

>Links of sources:

NCERT Physics class XII part 2, November 2021 Kartika 1943.

Simple Snippet

17 June 2016

Basic Logic Gates - OR | AND | NOT | XOR gates
| Boolean Algebra

https://youtu.be/NfX5aSvP_gA

Simple Snippet

5 February 2018

XNOR Gate in Boolean Algebra with Truth Table
and Equation

<https://youtu.be/uR9CmJE130s>

Simple Snippet

17 June 2016

Universal Logic Gates - NOR gate| Boolean
Algebra & Logic Gates

https://youtu.be/LRVX7E8_pAc

NOT gate Youtube:

<https://www.youtube.com/shorts/mKj6jTq21OM?feature=share>

Wikipedia logic gates:

XOR:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/XOR_gate?wprov=sfla1

OR:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/OR_gate?wprov=sfla1

NOR:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NOR_gate?wprov=sfla1

XNOR:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/XNOR_gate?wprov=sfla1

NOT gate Wikipedia:

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inverter_\(logic_gate\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inverter_(logic_gate))

NAND:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NAND_gate

NOT gate image from the internet:

https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fbmet.fandom.com%2Fwiki%2FLogic_Gates&psig=AOvVaw1JdRREuNgJF0qQEx1-Rlcb&ust=1702664889232000&source=images&cd=vfe&opi=89978449&ved=0CBIQjRxqFwoTCOi6ppLHj4MDFQAAAAAdAAAAABAD

Wikipedia Boolean algebra:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boolean_algebra?wprov=sfla1

>Appendix:

O-OR gate

X-X gates

A-AND gate

N-NOT gate

>License details:

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